

Figure 1. Overview of the golden rules for building sustainable bioinformatics capacity using nextflow and nf-core, with a focus on EMCRs. Based on the experience of The Kids, the process begins with Rule 1 (Strategic Plan), Rule 2 (Promote Awareness), Rule 3 (Needs and Skill Gaps), and Rule 4 (Engagement with IT and Documentation). Various events described in the remaining rules are distributed throughout the year, with key milestones highlighted in each quarter. This information is documented in the Nextflow-BioWiki (<https://github.com/TelethonKids/Nextflow-BioWiki>) (Agudelo-Romero et al., 2023).

